

Book Reviews

KAUSHIK, B (Ed.) (2019): *Creating Inclusive Schools: Theory, Process, and Practice*, New Delhi: Sage Publication. pp. 282, Price: ₹ 325.00

Inclusion in education is a dynamic discourse that does well in theory but malfunctions at the level of implementation. This is evident from the present state of our education system, particularly of the school infrastructures, which are in practice more exclusive than inclusive as certain sections are still sidelined. Although successive government policies have led to steady progress in this regard, those from socio-economically disadvantaged groups (SEDGs) continue to face many challenges. According to National Education Policy 2020, there are 32 million out-of-school, in the age group of 6 to 17 in the country and majority of them are from marginalised socio-economic groups and under developed regions. National Education Policy (NEP 2020) addresses this issue and put major emphasis on access, participation and learning outcome of SEDGs.

The book under review is thematically organised into ten chapters, each dealing with a specific domain of inclusion. It attempts to shed light on the barriers and the broader concept of inclusive education by including other non-physical forms of disabilities such as the disadvantaged groups, low-income families, including poor children, siblings of the disabled, and girls within its definition. In the chapter "Conceptualising Inclusive Education," Bharti Kaushik and Abhishek Kumar Srivastava highlight in detail the concept of inclusive education, its need, benefits, and the factors supporting inclusion in education. The authors postulated that to address the issue of inequality and diversity in Indian classrooms — whether in terms of infrastructures or of the techniques of teaching, evaluation and examination, one must lay due emphasis on the inclusion of the children with special needs (CWSN). Although the concept advanced by the authors is fairly understood and perceived, inclusion in education is a dynamic subject that will continue to provoke debates and discourses even in the future. To ensure inclusive education, we need to delve deeper, beyond a mere comprehension of the concepts and go to the issue of their actualisation in practice, no matter what be the pace of progress.

In the chapter titled "Inclusion and Children with Disabilities," its author, Abhishek Kumar Srivastava, segregates and defines the concept of special education, integrated education, and inclusive education. The author argues that the shift in thinking, attitude, and treatment of those people with disabilities has improved in their favour in course of time. However, grassroots analysis reveals that attainment of inclusiveness in letter and spirit is still far from reality. CWSN and those from the more disadvantaged groups are still being sidelined. Society's callous approach and deputing 'inclusion' as the state's responsibility perpetuates their exclusion. Another reason could be the lack of familiarisation with the discourse on disability, which is still at its nascent stage and is yet to find its footing into the system.

The five succeeding chapters — third, fourth, fifth, sixth, and seventh — are authored by Bharti Kaushik, the editor of the book. In the chapter titled “Children with Diverse Needs,” she brings to the fore the various forms of disabilities suffered by a child in society. Recognition of siblings of children with disabilities and their plight in this chapter enriches and broadens our scope of looking at inclusion. To corroborate the idea of inclusive schools, the role of teachers trained in inclusive education is significant, which to our context is one critical domain that still requires pragmatic engagement.

The following chapter, titled “Special Needs and Teaching-Learning Strategies,” identifies the various strategies to be adopted to address the learning needs of the child as per their disability. This is critical to make classrooms accommodative and inclusive so that the specific needs of the child may thus be taken into account. Failure to ensure inclusiveness in our education system is often due to the overemphasis laid on theory in comparison to practice and due to evasion of responsibilities at the level of practice. The book, in that perspective, acts as a reminder to contextualise the learning needs of the child to address the issue of non-inclusion. Sustaining this practice will enable us to go a long way.

The chapter titled “Inclusive Schools” posits that while much preparedness is observed in case of the physical infrastructure so as to make regular schools more inclusive, the curriculum pedagogy must be suitably adapted and teacher-educators must be trained to move a step closer to reality. The chapter exposes the lacuna in teaching, the infrastructural gaps and the lack of community involvement and support in making our schools inclusive. Although the infrastructural modification of the existing regular schools to an inclusive school may be a viable task, the creation of an ideal inclusive school with the required resources, skills and expertise is a feat that will require a much more vigorous commitment than envisaged. The current state of inclusive education in despair is an indestructible testimony that demands renewed and focussed attention.

In the chapter “Policy Perspective, Provisions and Institutions,” the author lists the major initiatives taken by the state to include the CWSN. The author observes that the various acts, institutions and schemes to uplift this section of society have begun to produce benefits. However, the percolation of such benefits for CWSN is not widespread; rather it is limited to those living in the urban areas while those in the margins are often overlooked. Their hope for emancipation is often short-lived, thus perpetually cementing their status quo.

In the chapter “Inclusive Pedagogical Practices,” the author accords special attention to making the curriculum accessible to all students by using a learner-centered and need-based evaluation approach. The adaptation of a Universal Design for Learning (UDL) in the classroom settings to address the “one-size-fits-all” conundrum is a good step in this regard. However, to customise a differentiated instruction to address pedagogical exclusivity is an arduous task, but attainable if teachers are efficiently trained and equipped. In addition to making the pedagogy inclusive, the success of inclusive education requires multi-level support. The next chapter of the book under review, titled “Support Services,” acknowledges this reality. The author, Hillol Mukherjee, cites the importance of resource support — of material, human, information, and financial resources. In addition to these resources, the parents of a child can act as a mediator in enabling schools and classrooms to be inclusive. Since the major portion of responsibility rests upon the teachers of the school, no support system will see its day without the close partnership of the teachers and the parents.

Present-day regular and inclusive schools are deprived of one or more of these support systems, if not of all.

In the chapter “Assistive Technology and Continuous and Comprehensive Education,” the authors, Manoj Kumar and Bharti Kaushik, contend that Assistive Technology (AT) should be viewed as a tool for easing the access to the curriculum, and as an alternative to the traditional education’s methods of examination. This is imperative to make the exams free from stress, fear and trauma. Although the authors assert that many AT devices are inexpensive and not complicated, the assertion might not be true at the level of implementation. Due to the high cost that may be involved, customising an alternative solution specific to the context may be worth contemplating. In addition, it may be too overambitious to embark on continuing and comprehensive evaluation (CEE) as an alternative to the traditional method of examination and guarantee the same to be stress-free, as argued in the chapter. In his chapter “Role of Stakeholders,” Bharti Kaushik highlights the roles and responsibilities of various stakeholders associated with a school and the critical importance of their mutual collaboration. The author elucidates that understanding the nuances involved will pave a clear pathway for achieving the goals of inclusive education. It is the stakeholders' attitude of neglect and the incoherent relationship amongst them that have made inclusive education a difficult task to accomplish. The responsibilities need to be shared while taking due cognisance of all forms of disabilities that student body may face. Starting from the parents and siblings in the family to all other allied stakeholders within the community, a comprehensive partnership must be established to bring inclusive education to fruition.

The book under review makes an important contribution in the context of NEP 2020 which emphasises inclusive and equitable education for all. The richness of the book lies in its detailed analysis on inclusion in education. It does great justice to the readers by informing them about the concept of inclusive education at a crucial juncture, both microscopically and comprehensively. It is felt that there is immense scope to elaborate the methodology and clearly spell out core objectives at the beginning of the book. The book is a good reference book for policymakers, administrators, scholars, and educators working on inclusive education.

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